

THE EFFECT OF INITIAL POROSITY AND PARTICLE CLUSTERING ON THE TENSILE FAILURE OF CAST PARTICULATE MMCs

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ABSTRACT

Castings of an Al-9%Si alloy, reinforced with 20vol% of SiC particles, have been studied with and without prior secondary consolidation operations. Porosity levels have been measured by densitometry and specimens have been subjected to tensile testing at room temperature. All of the specimens from batch casting techniques showed low tensile strengths and ductilities, even though their initial porosity levels were fairly low (~1-1.5%). HIPing of these specimens reduced the porosity levels and resulted in relatively small increases in strength and ductility. DC cast material, which had a finer microstructure and lower porosity level than the shaped castings, showed a higher strength but similarly low ductility. Extrusion of this material, however, led to a substantial increase in ductility. This is attributed to the removal of particle clustering, which was present in all of the other material examined. It is concluded that the presence of particle clusters is highly detrimental to the ductility and damage tolerance of particulate MMCs.

INTRODUCTION

Failure in discontinuously-reinforced MMCs is often associated with the formation and growth of voids at the reinforcement-matrix interface[1, 2]. These voids subsequently coalesce by a ductile tearing mechanism, resulting in failure of the composite. Previous work[3-5] has established that stable voids can exist well before failure in these materials, and has suggested that the geometry of the reinforcement strongly influences void nucleation. Regions of matrix adjacent to the reinforcement, along the line of applied stress, are sites where high hydrostatic stresses are generated and hence where the nucleation of cavities is expected[4, 6-9]. Damage can also be initiated by reinforcement cracking. This is more likely when the reinforcement is larger[10] or has a high aspect ratio.

Much of the previous work in this area has been on material subjected to deformation processing, such as extrusion. There is an increasing interest in using MMCs in the as-cast condition. Cast material usually has a more inhomogeneous reinforcement distribution and a higher porosity level. An initially higher porosity level has been shown to accelerate the onset of failure in steels[11]. Furthermore, the inhomogeneous distribution of reinforcement commonly found in cast MMCs can promote damage due to increased constraint on matrix plasticity. There has been at least one report[12] that the ductility of cast particulate MMCs can be increased substantially by extrusion, although no explanation for this effect has been clearly identified.

In the present work, mechanical properties of as-cast composite are compared with those of material which has subsequently been extruded or Hot Isostatically Pressed (HIPed). Extrusion can align the reinforcement particles and give rise to a more homogeneous distribution, while HIPing is expected to eliminate much of the initial porosity.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

COMPOSITE PRODUCTION

A 20 vol% SiC particulate-reinforced Al alloy composite, provided by Duralcan (San Diego, California) was used in this investigation. The composition specification of the matrix, in weight percent, is 8.5-9.5 Si, 0.2 max Fe, 0.2 max Cu, 0.45-0.65 Mg, 0.2 max Ti, 0.03-0.1 other elements, remainder Al. The composite was manufactured by stirring the ceramic particles into the molten matrix. The castings were made using several techniques and various types of secondary processes were then applied. Details are given in Table 1. Hot Isostatic Pressing (HIPing) was carried out at a temperature of 450°C and pressure of 223 MPa for approximately 1.5 hours.

Casting Process	Condition of Material Studied
Sand Mould	As-cast Cast / HIPed
Permanent Mould	As-cast Cast / HIPed
Lost Foam	As-cast Cast / HIPed
Investment	As-cast Cast / HIPed
DC (Direct Chill) semi-continuous	As-cast Cast / Extruded

Table 1 Casting and processing conditions for Al-9wt%Si / 20 vol% SiC_p composites.

MECHANICAL TESTING

Tensile testing was performed under displacement control on a Schenck 10 kN screw driven machine. Dumb-bell shaped specimens were used, with a gauge length of 19 mm and approximate cross-sectional area of 9 mm². The crosshead speed was 0.2 mm min⁻¹, giving a strain rate of 2×10^{-4} s⁻¹ for the specimen gauge length used. Specimen strain was monitored using strain gauges, several being affixed after varying degrees of prior plastic strain when ductilities were high enough to warrant this.

MICROSTRUCTURAL OBSERVATION

Specimens were examined using optical and scanning electron (SEM) microscopy. Standard preparation and imaging procedures were used, but the study of cavities in the SEM was done on carefully electropolished samples, in order to minimise surface damage during preparation. Struers A2 electrolyte was used, with polishing at 20 V for 10 seconds. Specimens were given a coating of gold and examined using a low accelerating voltage of 13 kV.

DENSITY MEASUREMENT

Specimen density was measured using an Archimedean technique. A Sartorius RC210P microbalance with a sensitivity of ± 10 μ g was used. A high density fluorocarbon was used as the immersion fluid. Using this method, the density could be determined to within $\sim 0.02\%$. In order to monitor any cavitation during tensile straining, some tensile tests were periodically interrupted and density measurements carried out.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

INITIAL POROSITY

The measured porosity levels of the composites under investigation are shown in Fig.1. The values were calculated relative to a theoretical density of 2.77 Mg m^{-3} . The columns labelled 'As-cast' and 'Cast / HIPed' are average values for the sand, lost foam, investment and permanent mould castings. Specimens from these castings did show variations in void content, but no systematic trends were observed and most values were fairly close to the average value shown.

Figure 1. Initial void contents of MMC material, calculated from measured density values, using a fully dense value of 2.77 Mg m^{-3} .

Figure 2. SEM micrograph showing a large pore in an as-cast (lost foam) specimen.

It is clear that the specimens from shaped castings had the highest initial porosities. It was possible to see pores in many of these samples with the naked eye ($\sim 300 \mu\text{m}$). SEM observation revealed both large and small pores in all of the shaped castings. Fig.2 shows an example of a large pore, taken from a lost foam casting. HIPing reduced the measured porosity levels and indeed fewer pores were seen in the SEM in the cast / HIPed specimens. The DC cast and DC cast / extruded composites had the lowest initial porosity levels and few pores were visible in the SEM in these specimens.

PARTICLE DISTRIBUTION

An impression of the particle distributions in the different composites can be obtained from the micrographs shown in Fig.3. Regions of dense particle clustering can be seen in the lost foam as-cast sample. This was also typical of the sand, investment and permanent mould castings. The SiC particles have been rejected and pushed ahead of the solidification front, to be trapped by the finally converging dendritic arms in the inter-dendritic regions[13]. As expected, HIPing had little effect on the particle distribution, although some of the pores were eliminated, as mentioned above. Voids were often found associated with severe clusters, both in the as-cast and HIPed material, as illustrated in Fig.4.

The severity of clustering was lower in the DC casting, due to the faster solidification rate and consequently smaller dendrite arm spacing. Extrusion created a much more homogeneous distribution of particles - see Fig.3(d). The particles also became aligned along the extrusion direction, as did the silicon platelets present in the matrix.

Figure 3. SEM micrographs showing particle distributions in (a) As-cast (lost foam), (b) Cast / HIPed (lost foam), (c) DC cast and (d) DC cast / extruded specimens.

MECHANICAL TESTING

Stress / strain curves are shown in Fig.5. The as-cast and cast / HIPed specimens are from lost foam castings, but their behaviour can also be taken for these purposes as broadly representative of the shaped castings.

Figure 4. SEM micrograph showing voiding in a region of dense particle clustering, taken from a Cast / HIPed (lost foam) specimen.

Figure 5. Stress / strain curves for four types of specimen.

It can be seen that extrusion significantly increased the failure strain of the DC cast composite (from ~0.8% to ~7%). The as-cast sample had the lowest strain to failure (~0.7%). HIPing was found to increase both the failure strain (to ~1.5%) and load bearing capacity of the lost foam cast sample.

DAMAGE MECHANISMS

As-cast Shaped Castings

There were no significant differences in the behaviour of the sand, lost foam, investment and permanent mould castings. All had similar failure strains (around 0.7%) and load-bearing

capacities. SEM examination of failed samples showed little difference from the corresponding samples before testing. There was no obvious increase in the number or size of voids after testing. However, as mentioned earlier, the castings had significant initial porosity, including some very large pores, which would be likely to initiate brittle fracture. The ceramic particles also tended to be highly clustered. In regions of high particle content, the degree of triaxial constraint on matrix deformation will be greater, favouring damage such as cavitation and particle fracture.

Cast / HIPed Composites

HIPing increased the failure strain of all of the castings to ~1.5%. There were also significant increases in tensile strength,. This might have been due to an increase in interfacial bond strength during HIPing. The HIPing process did reduce the porosity of the castings, but despite this, the failure strain remained fairly low. However, as mentioned earlier, HIPing did not alter the particle distribution. The reinforcement was still highly clustered and such regions of high particle concentration are likely to be favoured sites for damage development and subsequent fracture initiation.

DC Cast Composites

These castings exhibited similar failure strains to those of the shaped castings. However, they were significantly stronger. The greater strength can be attributed to the finer scale of the (dendritic) structure and the absence of large pores. However, particle clustering was still present and this apparently leads to cavitation and failure at relatively low strains.

DC Cast and Extruded Composites

The extrusion process aligns the reinforcement particles and generates a more homogeneous spatial distribution. This led to substantially higher ductilities. SEM observations revealed that failure had occurred by a void growth and coalescence mechanism. Voids formed in the matrix adjoining individual reinforcement particles and at the occasional cracked particle - see Fig.6. Voids were mainly observed near the fracture surface, although voiding in the few clustered regions was found along the full gauge length.

These observations are confirmed by the void content evolution data in Fig.7. These data suggest that the extruded material is much more tolerant of the formation of voids than is the DC cast material. The implication is that, in the absence of particle clusters, voids can form at individual particles without immediate danger of failure, whereas the clustered regions in the DC cast material are sites where damage quickly becomes concentrated and leads to fracture.

Figure 6. SEM micrographs from near the fracture surface of a DC cast / extruded specimen, showing (a) voids in the matrix adjoining SiC particles and (b) voids at cracked particles.

Figure 7. Measured increase in porosity level with plastic strain for DC cast and DC cast / extruded composites.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn from this work

- Castings of particulate MMCs produced by various techniques have been examined metallographically and subjected to tensile testing, with and without prior secondary processing operations.
- All of the shaped castings, in the as-cast state, tended to fracture at low stresses (~150-200 MPa) and to have low ductilities (~0.5-0.8%). Their initial void contents were relatively low, at around 1-1.5vol%. They exhibited a substantial degree of particle clustering, largely attributable to particle pushing during dendrite growth.
- Hot isostatic pressing of these shaped castings reduced the initial void content substantially, although the degree of particle clustering was unaffected. Some improvements in tensile strength and ductility were also produced by this operation, but the increases were relatively small.
- DC cast material had lower initial porosity contents and a finer microstructure than material produced by the batch casting techniques. Particle clustering was still present. It was found to be significantly stronger and slightly more ductile than the shaped castings.
- Extrusion of the DC cast material led to alignment of the ceramic particles and removal of the clustering. A large increase in the tensile ductility (from 0.8% to 7%) resulted from the extrusion operation.
- It may be concluded that clustering of ceramic particles is a very important factor in determining the ductility and toughness of particulate MMCs. The matrix is

highly constrained within clusters and prone to cavitation, leading quickly to large defects which can become sites for fracture initiation. The removal of clustering by suitable thermo-mechanical processing can give important improvements in ductility and damage tolerance.

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